

IDENTIFYING STUDENT INTERNSHIP RISKS USING THE QUESTIONNAIRE METHOD

Author(s)*: Anca-Vasilica MATEUCA (DORNEANU)¹, Dana Elena MORAR²

Position: PhD Student¹, Lecturer²

University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca

Address: Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului St., No. 28, Romania

Email: anca28.01dorneanu@gmail.com¹, Dana.Morar@ccm.utcluj.ro²

Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – The internship that students enter upon concluding framework agreements between educational establishments (internship organizers) and various economic agents (internship partners). This activity is especially important, as it is also regulated from a legal standpoint through Law no. 258/2007. In order for this activity to fully achieve its goal, and in order for it to be carried out in optimum conditions, aside from heeding the legal provisions, an awareness of the risks that may occur and the possibilities to remove and manage them is also necessary.

Methodology / Approach – Students' internships precede their activity as future employees, and are meant to acquaint them both with the professional aspects of the domain that they will be active in, and also with matters related to occupational health and safety. As such, it is very important for students to be aware and informed when it comes to the dangers and risks that they are contextually exposed to when carrying out their internship, and the methods to control the risks to their health, as well as their colleagues'. Furthermore, all parties that have a role in the conduct of the students' internship must be involved in the risk prevention activity.

Findings – The questionnaires were created after analyzing the vocational training standards and potential risk factors identified in internship activities.

Research limitations / implications – The purpose of this article is to identify the risks that can affect student activity and health during their internship and establish concrete and efficient measures to prevent them by using the questionnaire method.

Practical implications – The practical importance of the endeavor backing this article cannot be denied. The internships undertaken by the students do not only aim for the acquisition of new theoretical skills, as mentioned succinctly above, but also entail the molding of practical abilities through the specialized training and the accommodation of the students with the professional domain that they will be active in. As such, it is important for student internship activities to be carried out in a context that is as similar as possible with the one that they will be working in, and for their training to be carried out in accordance with certain vocational training standards that comply with the labor market requirements.

Originality / Value – Internships are an important step in the future development of the students, but they must be conducted in conditions of utmost safety to them. Students' training on the possible risks can be carried out much more efficiently if the OSH norms are included in the school curriculum and if the information presented to the students corresponds with the current knowledge in the domain. By drawing up the questionnaires described in this article, we have attempted to identify the most important risks related to occupational health and safety and, correspondingly, the best prevention methods that must exist at educational establishment and economic agent partner level.

Keywords: internship, risk factors, questionnaire

Introduction

Students' internship activity represents the congruence of the common efforts of professional and technical educational institutions, and economic agent partners. The conduct of students' internship in good conditions entails the correct identification of the risks that may arise and the capacity to prevent them.

All parties involved in the preparation and conduct of students' internship (the school's management, internship coordinators, representatives of the economic agent partners, internship advisors, students) must be engaged in risk prevention in order to decrease the possibility of their emergence. To this end, labor protection training is imperative both for the educational establishment and for the economic agent partners, which should be conducted according to the occupational safety and health norms provided for in the legislation currently in force, as well as the institutions' own norms.

The students must be informed about the dangers, risks and risk control, they must recognize the dangers, evaluate the risks and adopt measures to control risks to their and their colleagues' health, as well as manage their environment well in order to ensure their health and safety, as well as others'. These skills can be developed through an initial training that is adequate for the environment where the internship is conducted, and an efficient level of communication between the school unit and the economic agent partner.

Risk prevention in school

The report concerning Occupational Safety and Health in the School Curriculum – Requirements and Activities in the EU Member States (<https://osha.europa.eu/publications/reports/TE3008521ENC/view> accessed on the 23rd July 2020) conducted by the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work reveals that, in order to support education related to the domain of occupational safety and health (OSH) in schools and colleges, it is necessary to make it official in the school curriculum. The report evaluates the manner in which the EU Member States have integrated OSH and the education focusing on risks in their national programs.

There are considerable activities and progress in primary education, as well as secondary education in what concerns the actions taken, as well as those planned by Member States. The actions that aim to integrate OSH into education at school curriculum level include:

- legal provisions;
- voluntary school programs;
- practical guides and informative resources supporting the application of the legal provisions and voluntary school programs;
- official recommendations;
- national practical guides and informative resources, in the event of a school curriculum not being set out;
- promotion campaigns supporting the integration of OSH into education;
- approaches meant for safe and healthy schools.

It is necessary for students to develop skills specific to risk-related education through practical courses in the curriculum:

- to be informed about dangers, risks and risk control;
- to recognize the dangers, evaluate the risks and adopt measures to control the risks to their health and the health of their colleagues;
- to use the information to evaluate immediate and cumulative risks;
- to manage their environment in order to ensure the health and safety of themselves and others;
- to explain the steps that need to be taken for risk control.

According to the above mentioned report, it is important to include risk education in the school curriculum, because young workers in Europe suffer a higher than average rate of non-fatal accidents at work, and are especially likely to have an accident in the first few weeks of starting a new job. Many young people enter the labour market with little or no knowledge of workplace risks and preventive measures, therefore safety risk education should be a part of their schooling. Also, we believe that teaching them Occupational Safety and Health will enable their active and conscious participation in this process as future employees, because the employers cannot take the necessary actions without the involvement of the workers (Moțiu, 2012).

The problems of the professional and technical educational system identified by the Romanian Academy, the “Costin C. Kirițescu” National Institute of Economic Research, the Institute for the Research of Quality of Life in “Învățământul profesional și tehnic. Provocări și perspective de dezvoltare. Raport de politică publică” -“Vocational and Technical Education. Development Challenges and Perspectives. Public Policy Report”- (<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/310609289> accessed on the 25th July) are generally related to the curriculum and the presented instruments / devices / technologies, which are not adapted to our current reality:

- The quality of the curriculum and learning instruments
- The existing vocational training standards in the VTE system (vocational and technical education) are “obsolete,” as they are not updated according to the requirements of the labor market, both in what concerns the description of the profession, as well as the presentation of the skills which should be attained by the end of the graduates’ studies. These vocational training standards lie at the foundation of establishing qualifications, and are extremely important especially to employers who have an interest in involving themselves in the support of certain specializations in the VTE system that are necessary for their activity. Some employers have complained that they have requested certain qualifications from VTE institutions for which classes could not be organized due to the absence of these standards, while the process of devising new ones takes upwards of even two years.
- Failure to update standards has effects on the curriculum modification process (school programs, education plans, etc.). Failure to modify the curriculum leads to outdated notions and techniques being taught with the help of outdated equipment.
- The learning instruments used (manuals, learning methods) do not correspond with the current knowledge in the domain. The manuals are only updated after the modification of the curriculum. Some employers have become involved in the re-updating of the manuals and the creation of learning instruments (students’ notebooks, evaluation sheets), but the process to their being recognized at national level is extremely bureaucratic and lengthy.

An adequate training of the students in what concerns identifying and managing the risks that may appear during their activity must also focus on the types of accidents that may occur wherever they are conducting their internship, as well as occupational diseases.

Formulating the questionnaires

1. Analysis of the vocational training standards

The analysis of the vocational training standards was conducted with a view towards the importance given to the occupational protection and safety of the students during the practice activity carried out at school and with the economic agent. This analysis has revealed two main aspects:

A. The vocational training standards describe the skills / units of outcome that will be developed for the students after completing the modules specific to each vocational qualification. Each module entails the development of certain acquisitions for the students related to labor means, workload and work environment, so that they can efficiently exercise their profession. All of these elements generate risks in the practice activity, on top of which there are also the risks stemming from the students, depending on their ability and interest for their vocational development.

B. One category of risks that is not taken into consideration: psychosocial risks that can negatively influence the learning process and the personal and professional development of the students. According to the Guide for Appreciating the Quality of the Evaluation of Risks and Risk Management Measures in Order to Prevent Psychosocial Risks (<https://www.inspectiamuncii.ro/documents/66402/267740/ANEXA+3Ghid+psihosociali.pdf/de999d2c-4fdc-46e2-bb85-b7d8c96e24a7>, accessed on 25th July 2020), numerous different types of psychosocial risks can have negative effects on the workers’ health and wellbeing. The most representative psychosocial risks are workloads that are too heavy, work rhythms that are excessively fast-paced, as well as negative social behavior, such as violence or harassment.

Examples of psychosocial risks:

- The activity itself: the monotony of work or the short work cycles; fragmented or pointless work, insufficiently used skills, heightened degree of uncertainty, permanent contact with difficult clients, patients, students, etc.
- The workload and work rhythm: oversized or undersized workload, rhythm determined by automation, increased levels of pressure related to time and the permanent pressure inflicted by deadlines
- Work schedule: working in shifts, night shifts, inflexible work schedules, unforeseen work time, prolonged hours or a schedule that is not adapted to social life
- Control: decreased degree of participation in the decision-making process, lack of control over the workload, work rhythm, working in shifts, etc.

Another aspect that is relevant for the practice activity of the students is how they communicate with the economic agents and clients. The vocational training standards include a module of professional communication specific to each qualification. The manner in which this module is taught and learned can generate risks or, on the contrary, prevent the emergence of risks in the student-economic agent or student-client relationship.

2. Formulating the questionnaires

Based on the analysis of the vocational training standards and identified potential risk factors, we have formulated three questionnaires, one for the students, one for the internship coordinators of the educational establishment, and, respectively, one for the internship advisors designated by the economic agent partner.

The purposes of the questionnaires consist in:

- identifying the most important risks that can occur during the practice activity, from the point of view of the possibility of their emergence and the impact that they have on the students;
- identifying the existing student health and safety measures for the practice activity at educational establishment and economic agent partner level.

The questionnaires are divided into four parts:

- Part I – Personal data;
- Part II – Risk identification;
- Part III – Assessment and prioritization;
- Part IV – Prevention and protection measures.

Part I allows the sampling of respondents based on gender, age, class / seniority in education / seniority in student training and the domain of vocational training / activity.

Part II of the questionnaire was drawn up by focusing on five risk factor categories identified through the analysis of the vocational training standards:

1. Risk factors related to the work means: wear and tear of work devices and tools; contact with toxic / flammable substances; direct contact with sharp, prickly, slippery, contaminated surfaces; contact with faulty sources of electrical current; fires; allergic and irritant reactions caused by the protection equipment;
2. Risk factors related to the work environment: increased noise; air temperature in the space where the activity is carried out (too high / too low); toxic gases, vapors, aerosols, microbes, viruses, bacteria; exposure to biological products; exposure to radiation;
3. Risk factors related to the workload: lack of training for emergency situations; attention that is permanently solicited during work; physical (musculoskeletal) overexertion; poor communication with the clients; inadequate distribution of workload to the students (in a barked manner, with no explanations or details, with no feedback);
4. Risk factors related to the executor: investing little importance into the occupational protection training; failure to respect the internship distribution based on the skills gained; incorrect

operation of the devices and tools; incorrect usage of the protective equipment; errors when applying the procedures for the reporting of incidents;

5. Psychosocial risk factors: workloads that are too heavy; excessively fast work pace; negative social behavior, such as violence, harassment, threats; monotony of the work; insufficiently used skills.

For every category of risk factors, we have established five risks that are common for several professional qualifications, allowing respondents to add two more risks. Each risk shall be assessed according to the possibility of its occurrence and its impact, on a Likert scale of 1 to 5, where 1 = does not occur / has no impact, 2 = occurs rarely / low impact, 3 = occurs sometimes / medium impact, 4 = occurs frequently / high impact, 5 = always occurs / very high impact.

Part III of the questionnaire aims to establish a hierarchy of the ten most important risks in order of possibility of their occurrence and impact on occupational safety and health. Based on the frequency of the answers, the most mentioned risks shall lie at the foundation of the coming measures ensuring occupational safety and health.

Part IV of the questionnaire focuses on identifying the existing risk prevention measures in the internship activity of the educational establishment and the economic agents. The answers will offer an overall view on the importance given to the measures to ensure the health and safety of the students during their internship by the internship organizer and the economic agent partner.

After implementing the questionnaires and interpreting the results, we will have a clear view on the existing risks that can negatively affect the activity and health of the students during their internship, and we will be able to establish concrete measures to prevent these risks, as well as intervention procedures / protocols in cases where these risks occur.

Conclusions

Educational establishments can face the same risks as any other workplace. The specific workplace element of the educational sector is the presence of students or pupils. They can be vulnerable, as they are young, inexperienced and often unequipped with knowledge of the risks concerning their safety and health. The youth can also be a danger to themselves. An educational institution should be a safe and healthy work environment, conducive to education. In order to achieve this, the risk assessment must take into consideration the planning, organization and constitution of the work environment, and must especially take into account the presence of vulnerable groups (such as very young students).

In order to ensure an environment that is conducive to the development of the practical abilities of the students, we propose:

- identifying the risk categories specific to each professional qualification from the point of view of the teaching staff, students and representatives of the economic agent partners;
- establishing the risks bearing a real impact on the three categories of persons involved;
- determining the concrete prevention or intervention measures for these risks in order to diminish the negative consequences.

As a result of creating and implementing the questionnaires for the three categories of people involved in the internship activity, we shall be able to identify the most important risks that have a real impact on occupational health and safety. Based on these risks, we will be able to set prevention measures at school and economic agent partner level. The measures must be established in the procedures and protocols of the educational establishments and economic agent partners, and also at the level of student behavior and attitude through constant notifications and open communication.

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